

The First International Conference on Molecular Modeling and Spectroscopy

Abstract Book

19-22 February, 2019
National Research Centre, Cairo, Egypt

Tuesday February 19, 2019: New Hall, National Research Centre	
09:00-10:00	Registration
09:45-10:25	Opening Ceremony Prof. Medhat Ibrahim Prof. Ahmed Fakhry Prof. Mohamed Hashem President of the National Research Centre
10:25-10:30	Photo Session
10:30-11:00	Coffee Break
11:00-14:00	Session I: Prof. Ahmed Fakhry & Prof. Lotfia ElNadi OL-05 to OL-11 & O-35 to O-37
14:00-15:00	Lunch
15:00-17:30	Session II: Science for the Society: Science Café: Prof. Medhat Ibrahim & Prof. Osama Osman O-20 to O-34
14:45-17:00	Session II: Prof. Hanan Elhaes (Hall D) O-38 to O-46
09:00-18:00	Session III: Poster: P01-P42 (Hall V) Dr. Diaa Atta & Dr. Mohamed Taha
February 20, 2019: New Hall, National Research Centre	
08:30-10:10	Session IV: Prof. Hanan Elhaes & Prof. Abdel Aziz Mahmoud O-47 to O-52; OL-12
10:10-10:40	Coffee Break
10:40-13:55	Session V: Prof. Kholmurzo Kholmurodov & Prof. Wolfram Baumann OL-13 to OL-16; O-53 to O-56
14:00-15:00	Lunch
09:00-18:00	Session VI: Poster: P43-P86 (Hall V) Dr. Amr Abdelghany & Dr. Aly Okasha
15:00-18:00	Session VI: Prof. Mustafa Soylak & Dr. Sylwia Orzechowska OL-17; O-57 to O-70
February 21, 2019: New Hall, National Research Centre	
08:30-10:10	Session VII: Prof. Hanan Elhaes & Dr. Ahmed Refaat OL-18; O-71 to O-75
10:10-10:40	Coffee Break
10:40-13:30	Session VIII: Prof. Grigory Arzumanyan & Prof. Medhat Ibrahim OL-19; O-76 to O-81
13:30-14:30	Lunch
14:30-15:30	Session IX: Prof. Ahmed Fakhry & Prof. Pavel Gladyshev O-82 to O-85
15:30-16:15	Closing Ceremony & Recommendations

OL: Keynote Lecture

O: Oral

P: Poster

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OL-14: The Experimental and Molecular Dynamics Studies of the DNA Radiation Damage and Conformation Behavior on a Zirconium Dioxide Surface

Kholmirzo Kholmurodov^{1,2}, Aleksandr Doroshkevych¹, Nelly Doroshkevych¹, Tatyana Zelenyak², Elkhon Khamzin², Khaiyom Rahmonov^{1,3}, Dilshod Nematov⁴, Amondullo Burhonzoda⁴, Mirzoaziz Khusenov⁴ and Subrata Majumder⁵

¹Joint Institute for Nuclear Research, 141980, Dubna, Moscow Region, Russian Federation

²Dubna State University, 141980, Dubna, Moscow Region, Russian Federation

³National Research Nuclear University, MEPhI, 115409, Moscow, Russian Federation

⁴Tajik Technical University named after M.S. Osimi, 724000, Dushanbe, Republic of Tajikistan

⁵National Institute of Technology, N.I.T., Patna: 800 005, India

Email: mirzo@jinr.ru

This work is aimed on a complex study of the DNA immobilization and conformation processes on the zirconium dioxide (ZrO_2) surface. The DNA+ ZrO_2 nanoparticles and nano-sized films were investigated with the molecular dynamics (MD) modeling, and experimental spectral and integral methods, including nuclear physics. According to the spectroscopic analysis data, the DNA fragments were best interacted with nanoparticles in a 50% acetic acid medium (0.5 ml of 1/10 solution of $C_2H_5OH:CH_3COOH + 0.5$ ml of DNA). According to the electron microscopic data, the objects in the volume of a functional layer represent a two-level system potentially capable of responding to external electromagnetic influences. Using the MD hybrid classical and quantum chemistry potentials, for the DNA solvated with water the DNA+ ZrO_2 surface interactions were simulated. We have generated series MD models, thereby simulating a different scenario of the DNA with possible charge modifications. The DNA charge modification was introduced in the DNA central region via its two phosphorus atoms, P_a and P_b , and for several set of MD models for the relaxed DNA structures we have estimated the positional changes of the distance $D[DNA(P_a, P_b) - ZrO_2(O)]$ between the phosphorus atoms (P_a, P_b) and selected oxygen atoms of the ZrO_2 surface (see the Figures below).

Keywords: ZrO_2 ; MD simulation; DNA immobilization and Conformation processes

Figure. The system (DNA molecule and ZrO_2 surface) solvated with water.

Figure. The position of the DNA phosphorus atoms and oxygen atom of the ZrO_2 surface are shown.

Figure. The position of two phosphorus atoms (P_a and P_b ; grey color) as DNA damaged sites.

Figure. The $D[DNA(P_a, P_b) - ZrO_2(O)]$ distance between the (P_a) and (O) atoms for different MD models. (Model of damaged DNA): O (P_a, P_b) = 0

Figure. The DNA orientation dynamics on ZrO_2 for model of damaged DNA: $Q(P_a, P_b) = 0$.